

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE ESSAY IN CREATIVE THINKING IN THE PRIMARY CLASS

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Annotation: This article is about the use of the essay writing method in the education of elementary school students, the useful features of essays, and their types.

Key words: Essay, speech culture, thinking, creativity, ability.

Every academic activity, including writing an essay, requires serious work. Writing an essay is a literary work. Literary work requires a lot of mental and emotional strength from a person and requires a mature qualification. Students who comply with these requirements will develop their ability to think independently, choose and collect words and materials, express them in a logically interrelated manner, pay attention to spelling, and work discipline will be cultivated.

In general, the essay becomes an effective means of education only when literary work is properly organized. It develops students' interest in writing essays, enthusiasm, ability to observe, teaches them to correctly assess what they see and read books and fairy tales. Essay materials selected for primary grades are an opportunity for students to improve their skills in writing essays on literary topics, life experiences and visual arts will give. The growth of students' ability to independently approach the work of art, to evaluate it independently, to generalize materials, to study literary events in connection with the historical process, also creates an opportunity for writing essays on various topics in higher classes. Essay - to help students to understand narrative and dialogue, which are means of expressing their thoughts, to use them in students, to express their thoughts coherently, to use words and sentences in their place, to create and develop the skill of fluent style. will

help. In primary grades free essays at the end of the quarter require students to study the character, behavior, and labor of people in the environment, as well as observe social life and natural phenomena and think about them. Essays written on the basis of observation play an important role in cultivating the feeling of love for the Motherland and work in students, bringing them into the world of sophistication, connecting education with life, and serving to develop oral and written speech of students. Essay is the most effective tool for developing fluent speech. Improving speech culture is one of the tasks that requires independent work on the essay. In the process of preparing and creating an essay, the student observes new knowledge and skills, thinking, evaluation of literary life events, what he has read and mastered knowledge acquires a certain regulatory qualification. The educational value of the essay depends on the chosen topic, as well as on the independent work and interest of the students on the essay and the idea of the essay. The essay helps children to feel deeply about events, to think coherently teaches, increases their interest in language and literary creativity. Opening the ideological direction of the chosen topic allows solving the educational task. In this regard, topics about labor, heroes of labor, children's lives, school, village or city where they were born and raised, war heroes are especially convenient. The essay teaches how to organize the life of society. It cultivates love for nature, people, their aspirations and actions for good, the beloved and the product of labor, helps students to master the beautiful aspects of human behavior, and to understand the moral requirements of the present time.

To increase the educational value of the essay, it is necessary to observe the following:

Cultivating independence in students by regularly conducting oral and written essays in accordance with the principle of easy to difficult. Connecting the essay with life. Choosing a topic for the essay that is suitable for the educational duties of the school and the teacher. Increasing the emotional level of the work while working on the essay. When you say the word "homeland", the image of the place where you grew up as a child appears before your eyes. Essay on labor based on the material of a

field trip to production reveals new educational opportunities. In it, success and difficulties in the production of children, about advanced people, about professions and specialties, about technology information is used. In connection with the excursion to the production and the description of the work, it is necessary to talk about the profession, and it is reflected in this essay. Essay topics about work include "Our Village", "In the Garden", "To the Farmers", "Planting a Tree", "On the Farm". Essay is the highest form of creative work, it has a special place in school, all speech exercises are subject to essay in certain content. Essay in the 1st grade, starting with a small information and a passionate story, to express one's opinion it becomes a serious planned intellectual work that serves the formation of the student's personality and has educational and educational value.

Essay is a useful tool in the formation of personality, it arouses emotions and intellectual independence, thinking, evaluation of what one has seen and learned, observability, teaches to find cause-and-effect connections between events, to justify them, to draw conclusions. Essay organizes thoughts, gives students confidence in themselves, their strength and potential.

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